

The Importance of Correct Reasoning and Identifying Sophist Manipulation: A Critical Review of 'Visualizing Research' (2004) Gray, C. & Malins, J., Aldershot, UK: Ashgate.

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Overview

There is a case to be made for developing new approaches to research in visually based Art and Design domains. This book, however, does the opposite. Its use of fallacious reasoning and sophist rhetoric damages the case for committing resources to identifying new research approaches specifically suited to visual aspects of Art and Design. The book demonstrates a weakness in knowledge about research, and problematic thinking in the areas of analysis, reasoning, and research methods. These weaknesses are particularly significant in view of the book's intended role as a text for the training of new design researchers and guiding new research supervisors in Art and Design.

Building a case that research into visually perceived, culturally interpreted objects needs new research techniques requires intelligent correct reasoning identifying where, how and why the epistemological and practical characteristics of existing well-developed methods of data gathering and analysis are unsuited. This reasoning would provide the basis for identifying new research methods. In contrast, Gray and Malins have presented an approach to research based on false reasoning and what appears to be deliberate intent to persuade novice researchers and other readers of the authors' point of view by false arguments.

Reviewing the book has been hard, slow, and unpleasant. The central difficulty has been the need to elicit coherent meaning out of a structurally messy muddle of flawed logic, questionable evidence and sophism. This has required going through the book carefully several times on a word-by-word, sentence-by-sentence basis.

At first, I thought the difficulties might have been due to a problem in the collaboration between the authors. Perhaps each had written different parts of the book and the book had been rushed to press without adequate proofing. As I continued identifying and mapping out the problematic issues, it became clear that they were part of the authors' strategies to support their position. In many cases, the errors of reasoning are fallacies. Of additional concern, however, is what appears to be deliberate sophistry intended to bolster the authors' position and conclusions through deceit, false logic and manipulation of evidence.

The large numbers of problems of fallacious reasoning are particularly of concern because this is a book about how to do research. It is intended as a teaching text for postgraduates learning to do research and as such would be expected to demonstrate great examples in reasoning and thinking skills. In particular, because its focus is Art and Design domains, which the authors have identified as weak in formal research skills, the book would be expected to demonstrate positive examples of good formal

research approaches. Instead, the authors demonstrate a huge number of errors of reasoning. This is clearly not due to ignorance because the authors note that reasoning and critical thinking are essential to research.

Overview of the book structure

The book is 214 pages; it has a foreword by Mike Press; an Introduction; five chapters; four appendices; and a glossary.

The foreword starts with a special pleading that research in 'Art and Design' is different. In parallel, the authors also remind the reader that to date there has been a lack of methodological guidance and rigour in Art and Design practice-centred research and this has led to questionable outcomes. In the Introduction, the authors identify the primary aims of the book as the education of doctoral and masters students, supervisors and research managers and as a guide for postgraduate Art and Design students in undertaking the research process. The chapter introduces the central metaphor used in the book, that of research as a journey.

Emerging throughout the book, sometimes clear and at other times disguised, is the authors' agenda to persuade the reader that visual art practices should be regarded as research. The introductory chapter presents the initial foundations of this position by creating a pseudo-argument conflating Art and Design practices and research using the idea that both research and Art and Design practice can be regarded as journeys. The looseness of the journey metaphor is later exploited by the authors in support of their underlying perspective. They assume that because both visual art practices and research can be conceived of in terms of sharing a property, i.e. a journey, then this implies they are similar. This is the fallacy of the undistributed middle. It is more widely known in the childhood example of false logic: cats must be dogs because both have four legs.

The other chapters are:

Chapter 2. Mapping the Terrain: methods of contextualising research

Chapter 3. Locating your position: methods of orienting and situating research

Chapter 4. Crossing the Terrain: establishing appropriate research methodologies

Chapter 5. Interpreting the Map: methods of evaluation and analysis

Chapter 6. Recounting the journey: recognising new knowledge and communicating research findings

The four appendices comprise adaptations of others work. The glossary recoins research terms in ways relevant to the way the authors construe 'Art and Design' research.

The content of the chapters is evident from their titles and follows a conventional research process. In this review, I am not going to describe the chapters' content in detail. Instead, I want to draw attention to some of the main problems of flawed reasoning and sophist argument found throughout the book. These problems deeply compromise the book to such an extent that any discussion of content is almost irrelevant. There are problems this review does not address. In the main, these relate to the practical advice on research that the authors offer. In practical terms, the levels

of advice about specific research methods are better addressed by many other more general research training texts.

Problems that fundamentally compromise this book

Correct reasoning is central to research, to critical thinking and to creating useful knowledge that can be shared with others. Gray and Malins quote Eno (p.24) that, 'The Arts routinely produce some of the loosest thinking and worst writing known to history...' This book continues rather than redresses that tradition.

Change for the better, in research terms, requires careful attention to avoiding flawed reasoning, bias and deceit. There are three aspects to this:

- Avoiding fallacies: errors in the structure of reasoning leading to incorrect or unjustified conclusions
- Avoiding lack of reasoning: where things are asserted without proper explanation
- Never using sophistry: deliberate attempts to deceive the reader or persuade them to the authors' point of view through false reasoning, syllogism and biased or manipulated evidence

Fallacious, i.e. false, reasoning and sophist reasoning abound. Typically, the process the authors uses is to first build up scenarios that people will sensibly agree, then by a series of distractions (fallacies of distraction) and shifts in the use of meanings of the terms (fallacies of equivocation and amphiboly), they argue with false reasoning on the basis of what the less than careful reader would regard as apparently sound evidence.

In the book, I found on most pages between six and twelve errors of reasoning; problems of faulty understanding of concepts or research methods; and in some cases what appear to be deliberate manipulation intended to persuade by deceit any reader that does not pay careful attention. Much of this seems to locate around a process by which the authors first assume that visual art practise is research, and then build a weight of evidence in favour of this position, by whatever means they can: fair or foul. To enable their approach, this has needed them redefining key research terms such as 'analysis', 'argument', 'valid evidence' and 'research' in ways that differ from how they are used by other researchers. They derive support for redefinitions by selective quotation of a small number of authors.

Widespread in the book is the use of sophist manipulative techniques such as the use of syllogisms intended to persuade the reader of the authors' arguments, regardless of the problems with the underlying validity of the authors' reasoning or the validity of their evidence and assumptions. The authors use a range of techniques to distract and confuse the reader to get them to believe that the authors have in place a fully justified, reasoned argument when it is not so.

It concerns me that taking a broad and critical view across the text; it appears that this barrage of tricks is intended to persuade a reader who has not the time or skill to check carefully for false logic and weak evidence. The book is a text aimed at novice researchers, and should be beyond reproach in these matters. It is not. The primary

sophist technique used by the authors is to take the reader from apparently solid ground by subtle changes of meaning, fallacious arguments and carefully selected references, interposed by other material as a distraction, so that the authors are able to claim conclusions that are radically different from those that would be more normally deduced logically from the foundations from which they started.

The following sections of this review will describe some of the main problematic issues:

Reasoning

Reasoning is almost completely missing from this book, although at several points the authors briefly mention it is an essential foundation of the critical thinking central to competent research. Beyond this, however, the authors omit or almost completely ignore the role of correctness of reasoning in research and critical thinking.

Problematic redefinition of 'analysis'

The authors use a definition of 'analysis' that is very different from the way that it is generally used in research. To be fair, their use aligns with its strict etymology relating to breaking a 'whole' into distinct parts, a taxonomic view that is opposite to synthesis. Their 'new' use of the term analysis contrasts with the more usual perspective in research in which 'analysis' refers to developing a well-justified causal explanation of use by others. This usual research meaning of 'analysis' depends heavily on the use of correct reasoning. In contrast, Gray and Malins definition is only weakly related to reasoning.

Choosing a taxonomic definition of analysis supports Gray and Malins approach to building evidence for their position that 'art practice is research' because it allows them to claim that it is the researcher's personal opinion under the advice of their artistic peers that is the reference point for the correctness analysis as it is the subjective choice of 'which bits to break something into'.

The authors neglect to make it clear to the reader that their approach is clearly at odds with the extensive research literature in other disciplines. Together their approach on this combines a variety of fallacies of explanation, definition, motive in place of support, and distraction.

Problematic redefinition of 'argument'

Gray and Malins' description of the skill of building an 'argument' also ignores the role of correct reasoning in developing an arguable position. Instead of using reasoning, they suggest that researchers simply build up a weight of material that has been selected, snipped, reinterpreted from wherever it can be found to persuade the reader of the researcher's viewpoint, in the style of political manipulation. From the examples in which they themselves use evidence, it is apparent that they are proposing weaker standards of validity and avoidance of bias than are normal in research

Ignoring reasoning as a core research skill

A significant proportion of the book focuses on providing extensive guidance to new researchers about the key skills of doing research. This advice almost completely neglects reasoning skills. This is surprising because the authors point out that Art and Design students and researchers are weak in conventional areas of research such as critical reasoning skills, and, elsewhere, that reasoning and critical thinking are essential and central to research.

Role of reasoning in avoiding faulty thinking

The authors seem unaware of, or choose to avoid, the understanding that without a focus on correct reasoning, there is a sharp descent into the realm in which faulty thinking, sophism, flawed evidence and manipulation are used to gain the apparent agreement of readers. With this lack of attention to correct reasoning, the authors demonstrate page after page of confused thinking, flawed reasoning, category confusion, building arguments on false assumptions, lack of care with the validity of evidence, lack of attention to assumptions, using terms in ways contradictory to how they define them, misunderstanding the well-established meanings of research terms and concepts that are in widespread use, and apparently intentional sophist manipulative persuasion methods.

Misuse of the journey/travel metaphor

The authors use a journey metaphor throughout the book. In one role, it is used to tie the book together as a document. In another role, it underpins the central fallacious argument in the book that supports the authors' claim that art practice is research.

Removing the confusing and conflating factors the authors use to disguise the real logic, we find the classical three-statement fallacy of the excluded middle (see for example, Stephen Downes, Stephen's Guide to the Logical Fallacies, <http://datanation.com/fallacies/>)

Statement 1: 'Research can be thought of in terms of a journey'

Statement 2: AND 'Art and Design practice can be thought in terms of a journey'

Conclusion 3: THEREFORE 'Art and Design practices are research'.

The conclusion is false because sharing one attribute in common, in this case one inferred from opinion, does not confer equivalence in all attributes.

This is one of the classic fallacies, sophist if done intentionally, taught in secondary school classes about reasoning skills. In this book, the fallacy spreads over many pages and is combined with a range of other fallacies, mainly fallacies of distraction. It is false reasoning of the form:

Statement 1: 'All cats have four legs'

Statement 2: AND 'All dogs have four legs'

Conclusion 3: THEREFORE 'All cats are dogs'.

This conclusion is false because the property of ‘having four legs’ is shared by objects, some such as tables, being in different categories.

This fallacious reasoning, like the many other examples in the book, is a concern because the book is aimed at providing an example of research skills for novice researchers. It suggests either the authors themselves are not skilled at reasoning and analysis, or they are deliberately trying to manipulate the reader using sophism and syllogism.

Fallacies of Explanation

In undertaking their proposal for defining a new form of visualising research, the authors do not indicate to the reader the counter arguments and literatures, and the counter arguments of the current strong level of discussion within and outside design fields on conflating art-practice and research. This latter omission also shows use of two other classic sophist/fallacious techniques – fallacy by exclusion (ignoring evidence or argument to the contrary) and the straw man fallacy where the authors ignore the main arguments to the contrary and instead address only peripheral issues.

Special Pleadings

The authors make special pleading that visually based Art and Design is different and hence should not have to conform to the usual strictures of research. They suggest that because it is different from science, unlike other disciplines that are also different from science, the usual conventions of research should not apply.

In making their case, the authors appeal to sympathy, evidence from apparent authorities, biased selection of sources, slippery slope arguments, prejudicial language, and popularity. This combines a range of fallacious techniques of false appeals to authority, supplying motives rather than reasons, and fallacies of distraction.

Distilled to its essence, the core components of the special pleading appear to be:

- Visually based art practice should be considered as research
- That the usual criteria and standards of evidence and correct reasoning required in other disciplines need not apply
- That judgments about the quality of research should lie with the researchers and their artistic peers rather than independent research assessors

Supervision

Reading the book suggests the Gray and Malins do not value, or have little awareness of the importance of the role of supervision in research education because reference to the role of supervisors is almost completely absent. Recent research shows that tightly structured supervision is an important factor in achieving good research training outcomes. This would be expected to apply particularly to those with Arts and Design backgrounds without foundation research skills in reasoning and the critical thinking skills that underpin research. Where supervision is by Gray and Malins, they mainly

use the term ‘advisers’ who they typically define as artistic peers with competence in visual skills rather than in research training.

A key issue in research training is moderation of standards of awards across disciplines. Thus, it is expected that a PhD in say Environmental Science be moderated to much the same standard as a PhD in, e.g., Philosophy. Much of this moderation depends on an international body of examiner/supervisors skilled in research methods working across disciplines. It is unclear, and not addressed in this book, how the authors propose that moderation of research awards relating to visually based research areas can occur where supervision is undertaken by ‘advisers’ who are artistic peers with little or no research skills.

Reasoning based on unjustified assumptions

At several points in the book, the authors derive arguments from unjustified assumptions, building reasoning on an initial statement of the form ‘A *suggests* B’, or ‘one explanation of this phenomena *might* be...’ and then assume the outcomes of the reasoning are fully justified. This is a significant break with the conventions of critical thinking and research. It aligns however with the authors’ position, not conventionally accepted in research terms, that an argument is what you can persuade people of, and any evidence can be used in any way to persuade.

Widespread lack of attention to the requirements of ‘necessary and sufficient’ conditions:

The criteria of ‘necessary and sufficient conditions’ of a causal explanation is an important basis for a reader to be able to validate steps in the authors reasoning. Throughout the book, the authors ignore these criteria in the arguments they present. Without this, in most cases, it must be assumed the authors’ reasoning is incorrect, false or intended to delude the reader.

Sophist manipulative techniques in building argument

Several patterns of reasoning in the book imply sophist intent. One starts with a statement that describes a situation correctly said in understated ways and relatively hidden in the text. Then in a widespread and dominant way, the authors write as if something different were true and then build their claims on this whilst being in the position to refer to and the fact that they have written the ‘correct’ version. An obvious example of this is Gray and Malins definition of methodology. Another, slightly different, example is the contradictions in Gray and Malins’ position on the role of reasoning. On one hand, they state that ‘correct, valid reasoning is the core of critical thinking and critical thinking is the central skill needed in research. They then omit reference to reasoning skills and reasoning in all situations where it is central yet would go against their argument. A third example is the way the authors on one hand state that ‘art’ cannot fully state the complete details of the artists reasoning and argument, and on the other hand implicitly assume in many ways that visual representations contain reasoning. A fourth example, is the use of sophist techniques of elision, equivocation, amphiboly and accent to gradually over a number of paragraphs shift the meaning of a term, concept or argument in two parallel paths of

discourse to give the illusion of correct reasoning and develop an equivalence that supports the authors position. An example of the technique is as follows:

Start Path 1: Make a statement that research uses research methods

Start Path 2: Make a statement that art practice uses methods

Sophist Transition: In both paths start to use the term 'practice methods' as a substitute for 'research methods' and 'art practice methods'

Sophist Transition: Omit in both paths the prefixes 'research', 'art' and 'practice'

Sophist transition: Continue to use term 'methods' in similar ways in the parallel paths ignoring that they refer to epistemologically different entities.

Use a supporting distraction: For example, a side step into pointing to references, which refer to research as sometimes requiring creative steps.

Sophist transition connecting the two paths: Make tentative statement that art-practice methods are used as part of research (as in providing the evidence to which research data collection and research analysis methods will be applied). This brings the two sets of incommensurate concepts, which are by now using the same terminology, into conflating distance.

Use a supporting distraction: Actual distraction is irrelevant. The intention is to distract and reduce the attention and memory of the reader.

Make Claim: Claim that art-practice methods are the research methods in research relating to art-practice

There are several example of this sophist method in the book.

False reasoning through false appeal to authority

This is typically done by the authors supporting their arguments through selective use of evidence, use of partial quotations, or in some cases by reworking the material of others to support the authors' claims. On my second reading through the book, I realised it was advisable to carefully check the originals where the authors quote something they claim is 'based on' the work of others. An example is the appendices that quote Scottish Postgraduate education material. This appears to have been modified in ways that more easily support Gray's and Malins arguments. The appendices also demonstrate an additional point, that quoted material is used and chosen in a not un-biased fashion. Material on the same topic by, for example, a different research council such as the EPSRC would have gone against the authors' position.

False reasoning and sophist manipulation using category confusion and conceptual conflation

The book is marked by what appears to be sometimes deliberate and sometimes incompetent category confusion that makes illusory bridges across epistemologically different discourses. For example, 'content' is confused and conflated with 'process' and 'analysis' with 'presentation'. This confusion and conflation, deliberate or otherwise, is a foundation aspect of much of the sophist and fallacious reasoning argument. Another example, is where 'research method' is first used to mean 'method of data collection', which is later transformed into 'research methodology' (defined at one point as 'the study of research methods'), which is later transformed into 'anything that the candidate does in their research'. Then the term 'research' is dropped, and the primary focus of reference is to the candidate's 'methodology',

which is then transformed into ‘the candidate’s methods’ which then enables the claim that research comprises ‘art-practice methods that primarily focus on creative thinking’.

Validation of research by researchers personal opinion

In a category-confused discussion of logic and reasoning, the authors argue that the processes of logic and careful reasoning are identical to innovative creative thinking of an artist. Therefore, they claim that justification for the validity of research lies with the creative subjective opinions of the researcher and their artistic peers. This contrasts strongly with normal practice in research in which validation is undertaken objectively through formal process of checking the reasoning is correct based on the validity of evidence, and the necessary and sufficient role of logical steps that directly connect the evidence through contiguous, correct reasoning pathways to the conclusions that are drawn.

Sophist techniques to parry criticism

From a cynical perspective, it appears that the intent of some of the structure of the book is to provide the authors with a means of parrying criticism of sophism and false reasoning. At times, while reading the book, I felt that many elements were placed as ‘escape clauses’ of obfuscation to provide protection to challenges to the authors underlying claim that art-practice should be considered research. From this viewpoint, this protection from criticism, may be seen to underlie many of the selective quotations, false quotations, biased interpretations, false logic, flawed logic, ongoing lack of attention to reasoning, motivational pleadings for special conditions for sub-elements of the authors insistence that art-practice is research, restructuring of the meaning of the concept of research, omission of discussion of complex arguments that would contradict their key points, techniques of elision and manipulation to persuade their point, whilst including material that while in essence contradicts the main thrust of their arguments is minimised in importance in the text.

Conclusion

This book presents a case for a new visually based approach to research.

A significant problem is that the approach is deeply compromised in many dimensions by errors of reasoning. It seems to me that the book is also ethically tainted by sophist techniques of persuasion.

Both of these are problematic. Both highly compromise the book in its intended role as a textbook for new students. Both suggest that new researchers and postgraduate students should be discouraged from using this book as a guide – except of faulty reasoning of the sort that is unlikely to get them a research degree, (unless they can find examiners who have similar skills in reasoning!).

Personally, I am seriously concerned about the adverse potential of this book on the design research field and in compromising individual students’ research careers.

In supervision terms, the book is difficult to recommend. It offers examples of ways of behaving in research that I would regard as highly compromised, and insufficient to merit a research degree. This is ethically problematic, because this book is aimed at new researchers unlikely to have the critical thinking skills to identify the errors,

manipulations, elisions, false reasoning etc that underpins the authors' claims and proposals. Without adequate justification, the authors are asking research students to risk compromising their research careers and wasting their time and resources on an inadequate and problematically argued new form of practice that the authors claim should be counted as research – in spite of the widespread critical concerns about their position that 'art practice' is equivalent to 'research'.

The problems of fallacious and sophist reasoning in the book extend further. They cast a shadow over the already complete PhD theses referred to in the book as examples of good practice. It potentially acts reminder for canny examiners concerned with research quality to check a candidate's references to see if they have used this text.